

Second contribution to the *Litargus jakli* species group (Coleoptera: Mycetophagidae) from the Oriental Region

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Abstract: The following new species belonging to the *Litargus jakli* species group from the Oriental Region are described, illustrated and compared with similar species: *Litargus (Litargosomus) philippinensis* **sp. nov.** (Philippines); *Litargus (Litargosomus) kalimantanus* **sp. nov.** (Indonesia: Kalimantan).

Introduction

The *Litargus jakli* group species have been described from the Oriental Region (Háva 2023) and include five species (Háva 2021, Junk 2022, Háva 2023). During the determination of some unidentified material deposited in the Naturhistorisches Museum, Wien, two new species from The Philippines and Indonesia: Kalimantan Island belonged to *Litargus jakli* species group, were discovered and described.

Material and methods

The material is deposited in the following collections:

JHAC - Jiří Háva, Private Entomological Laboratory & Collection, Únětice u Prahy, Prague-West, Czech Republic;

NHMW - Naturhistorisches Museum, Wien, Austria (M. Seidel).

The size of beetles or of their body parts can be useful in species recognition and thus, the following measurements were made:

total length (TL) - linear distance from anterior margin of head to apex of elytra.

elytral width (EW) - maximum linear transverse distance.

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Specimens of the presently described species are provided with red, printed label with text as follows: „HOLOTYPE [or PARATYPE] *name of species* sp. nov. Jiří Háva det. 2024”.

Results

Genus *Litargus* Erichson, 1846 **Subgenus *Litargosomus* Motschulsky, 1858**

***Litargus jakli* species group**

***Litargus (Litargosomus) philippinensis* sp. nov.**

Figs. 1-3

Description. Male. Body measurements TL 1.9-2.0 mm, EW 1.0-1.1 mm; oblong-oval, subparallel-sided; weakly convex dorsally, weakly glossy; brown on dorsal and ventral surfaces, covered with short, yellow recumbent setation.

Head brown, finely punctate; covered by yellowish, recumbent setation; labrum brown; eyes prominent laterally in dorsal view, coarsely faceted and slightly emarginate near antennal insertions; antennae with 11 antennomeres, entirely brown with brown setation, antennal club with three antennomeres (Fig. 2); palpomeres brown, apical maxillary palpomere large, cylindrical.

Pronotum brown, flatt, rugose, with large and dense punctures, covered with yellow recumbent setation; widest at base, gradually narrowed anteriorly and posteriorly; anterior margin slightly arcuate; sides roundly arcuate; basal margin sinuate, without short and circular grooves on subbasal parts.

Scutellum broadly triangular, with short recumbent yellow setation.

Elytra brown without colour patterns, covered by yellow recumbent setation, elongate, subparallel-sided, narrowed from apical 1/4 to apex. Epipleuron brown, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Meta-meso ventrite brown, with yellow recumbent setation. Prosternal process broad.

Legs entirely light brown with light brown spines, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Tibiae with long brown spines apically.

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Abdominal visible ventrites brown, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Pygidium brown, covered with yellow recumbent setation.

Male genitalia (Fig. 3).

Female. Unknown.

Differential diagnosis. The new species differs from other known species belonging to the species group by the form of the body, structure of the antennae and male genitalia; it is externally similar to *L. jaechi* Háva, 2023, but differs from it by the structure of the antennae and the brown body.

Type material. Holotype (♂): Philippines, Mindoro, E Puerto Galera, Sabang, xi.1992, Jäch leg., (NHMW). Paratypes: (1 ♂): Philipp., Negros Isl., Mambucal, 12.2.1994, Seyfert leg., (NHMW); (1 ♂): Philippines, Luzon, Lucena City, 23.11.1992 at light, Jäch leg., (JHAC).

Etymology. Toponymic, named after the Philippines.

Litargus (Litargosomus) kalimantanus sp. nov.

Figs. 4-5

Description. Female. Body measurements TL 1.9-2.0 mm, EW 1.0 mm; oblong-oval, subparallel-sided; weakly convex dorsally, weakly glossy; brown on dorsal and ventral surfaces, covered with short, intermixed yellow and brown recumbent setation.

Head brown, with dense and coarse punctures; covered by yellowish, recumbent setation; labrum brown; eyes prominent laterally in dorsal view, coarsely faceted and slightly emarginate near antennal insertions; antennae with 11 antennomeres, entirely light brown with yellow setation, antennal club with three antennomeres (Fig. 5); palpi brown, apical maxillary palpomere large, cylindrical.

Pronotum brown, convex dorsally, rugose, with large and dense punctures, covered with intermixed yellow and brown recumbent setation; widest at base, gradually narrowed anteriorly and posteriorly; anterior margin slightly arcuate; sides roundly arcuate; basal margin sinuate, without short and circular grooves on subbasal parts.

Scutellum broadly triangular, with short recumbent yellow setation.

Elytra brown without colour patterns, covered by intermixed yellow and brown recumbent setation, elongate, subparallel-sided.

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Epipleuron brown, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Metameso ventrite brown, with yellow recumbent setation. Prosternal process narrow.

Legs entirely brown with light brown spines, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Tibiae with long brown spines apically.

Abdominal visible ventrites brown, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Pygidium brown, covered with yellow recumbent setation.

Male. Unknown.

Differential diagnosis. The new species differs from other known species belonging to the species group by the form of body and structure of antennae; externally similar to *L. jakli* Háva, 2021, but differs from it by the structure of antennae, narrow prosternal process and intermixed brown and yellow setation on dorsal surfaces.

Type material. Holotype (♀): Indon., W Kalimantan, Nanga Ela env., 700 m, Nanga Nyuruh, 4-10.7.1993, Schneider leg., (NHMW). Paratype (1 ♀): same data as holotype, (JHAC).

Etymology. Toponymic, named after the Kalimantan Isl.

List of *Litargus jakli* species group

Litargus horaki Háva, 2023

Distribution: Thailand, Vietnam.

Litargus jaechi Háva, 2023.

Distribution: Thailand.

Litargus jakli Háva, 2021

Distribution: Indonesia, Timor.

Litargus jejuoensis Jung, 2022

Distribution: South Korea, Jeju.

Litargus jendeki Háva, 2023

Distribution: India, Meghalaya.

Litargus kalimantanus sp. nov.

Distribution: Indonesia, Kalimantan.

Litargus philippinensis sp. nov.

Distribution: The Philippines.

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Figs. 1-3. *Litargus (Litargosomus) philippinensis* sp. nov.: 1- body, dorsal aspect; 2- antennae; 3- male genitalia.

Figs. 4-5. *Litargus (Litargosomus) kalimantanus* sp. nov.: 4- body, dorsal aspect; 5- antennae.

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